

Supplemental information

Phenylacetic acid metabolism in land plants: novel pathways and metabolites

Pavel Hladík^{1,2}, Federica Brunoni^{1,2}, Asta Žukauskaitė³, Marek Zatloukal³, Jakub Bělíček⁴, David Kopečný⁴, Pierre Briozzo⁵, Nathan Ferchaud⁵, Ondřej Novák^{1,2}, and Aleš Pěncík^{1,2,*}

¹Laboratory of Growth Regulators, Faculty of Science, Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic

²Laboratory of Growth Regulators, Institute of Experimental Botany, The Czech Academy of Sciences, Olomouc, Czech Republic

³Department of Chemical Biology, Faculty of Science, Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic

⁴Department of Experimental Biology, Faculty of Science, Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic

⁵Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, Institute Jean-Pierre Bourgin for Plant Sciences (IJPB), 78000, Versailles, France

* Corresponding author: ales.pencik@upol.cz

Figure S1: Representative MRM chromatograms of PAA-glc. Retention times of PAA-glc in 1 pmol of PAA-glc standard, 2 mg of Arabidopsis roots extract and 2 mg of Arabidopsis spiked with 10 pmol of reference standard.

Figure S2: PAA-Trp and PAA-Val identification. PAA-Trp (A) and PAA-Val (B) were measured in MRM mode using 2 mg fresh weight (FW) of pea cotyledons. Retention times were compared to reference standards. For confirmation, MRM product ion confirmation (PIC) scans were performed, and fragmentation spectra are shown for both standard compounds and endogenous metabolites.

Samples were prepared as described in the Methods section. After evaporation, samples were dissolved in 30 μ l of 10% methanol prior to LC-MS/MS analysis using an Acquity UPLC[®] System (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled to a Xevo[™] TQ MS triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters MS Technologies, Manchester, UK). Chromatographic separation was performed on a reverse-phase Kinetex C18 100A

column (50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm particle size; Phenomenex). The mobile phase consisted of methanol (A) and redistilled water (B), both containing 0.1% acetic acid. The gradient elution program was as follows: 0 min – 90% B, 11.5 min – 10% B, 11.75 min – 0% B, 14.75 min – 0% B, 15 min – 90% B. The total run time was 18 min with a flow rate of 0.3 ml/min. Samples were stored in an autosampler at 4°C, and the column was maintained at 30°C. An injection volume of 5 µl was used. The eluate was introduced into the electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in negative mode (ESI⁻) with the following optimized conditions: source/desolvation temperature, 150/600°C; cone/desolvation gas flow, 150/1000 L/h; capillary voltage, 1 kV; cone voltage, 20 V; and collision gas flow, 0.14 ml/min. Fragmentation of PAA-Trp (collision energy [CE] 20 V) and PAA-Val (CE 15 V) was detected using MRM PIC scans. Data were processed using MassLynx v4.2 (Waters MS Technologies, Manchester, UK).

Table S1: Conditions and parameters of HPLC-MS/MS method. For each PAA metabolite and its corresponding internal standard (IS) diagnostic MRM transition and CE were optimized. Additionally, retention time (RT), limit of detection (LOD), linear range and coefficient of determination (R^2) were measured and calculated. Analytes were detected by the MS instrument with optimised conditions as described: nebulizer pressure, 25 psi; drying gas flow and temperature, 14 l min⁻¹ and 130°C; sheath gas flow and temperature, 12 l min⁻¹ and 400°C; capillary voltage, 3.0 kv; nozzle voltage, 0 V.

Compound	MRM transition	IS	MRM transition	CE (V)	retention	LOD (pmol)	linear range (pmol)	R ²
					time (min)			
PAA	135.1 > 91.0	[¹³ C ₆]PAA	141.1 > 97.0	2	5	4.5 10 ⁻²	4.5 10 ⁻² - 90	0.9965
PAA-Asp	250.1 > 132.0	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Asp	256.2 > 132.0	10	2.9	4.5 10 ⁻³	4.5 10 ⁻³ - 90	0.9973
PAA-glc	297.3 > 91.0	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	19	3.9	4.5 10 ⁻²	9.0 10 ⁻² - 90	0.9904
PAA-Glu	264.1 > 146.0	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	12	3.7	9.0 10 ⁻²	9.0 10 ⁻² - 90	0.996
PAA-Leu	248.2 > 130.1	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	12	10.2	9.0 10 ⁻⁵	9.0 10 ⁻⁵ - 9	0.9985
PAA-Phe	282.2 > 164.1	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	14	10.7	4.5 10 ⁻⁴	4.5 10 ⁻⁴ - 9	0.998
PAA-Trp	321.2 > 203.1	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	14	10.2	4.5 10 ⁻³	4.5 10 ⁻³ - 9	0.9974
PAA-Val	234.1 > 116.1	[¹³ C ₆]PAA-Glu	270.2 > 146.0	12	8.3	4.5 10 ⁻⁴	4.5 10 ⁻⁴ - 9	0.9983

Table S2: Method validation in Arabidopsis extract. Validation was conducted according to the protocol described by Hladík et al., 2023. Method accuracy (expressed as % BIAS) and precision (expressed as % RSD) were assessed through a spiking experiment. Arabidopsis seedlings (10 mg, homogenized) were extracted in 1 ml Na-phosphate buffer, and the extracts from five samples were pooled. The pooled extract was divided into 200 µl aliquots, with each aliquot spiked with 5 pmol of stable isotope-labelled standards. Unlabelled standards (1 or 10 pmol) were then added to the aliquots. The samples underwent purification using an in-tip µSPE method, and the concentrations of analytes were measured by HPLC-MS/MS with isotope dilution. Additionally, a separate set of plant extracts was processed without unlabelled standards, allowing for the subtraction of endogenous auxin metabolite levels to calculate recovery rates. Each sample was analysed in five replicates.

Analyte	1 pmol			10 pmol		
	pmol	BIAS (%)	RSD (%)	pmol	BIAS (%)	RSD (%)
PAA	1.15 ± 0.42	-15	37	10.13 ± 0.68	-1	7
PAA-Asp	1.07 ± 0.11	-7	10	10.21 ± 0.30	-2	3
PAA-Glu	0.95 ± 0.15	5	16	9.60 ± 0.14	4	1
PAA-Val	0.92 ± 0.03	8	3	10.58 ± 0.34	-6	3
PAA-Leu	0.91 ± 0.05	1	5	11.25 ± 0.29	-13	3
PAA-Phe	0.97 ± 0.05	3	5	10.89 ± 0.33	-9	3
PAA-Trp	0.93 ± 0.03	7	3	11.09 ± 0.47	-11	4
PAA-glc*	8.46 ± 2.06	15	24	48.29 ± 1.54	3	5

* PAA-glc was spiked with 10 and 50 pmol

Table S3: Method validation in pea extract. Validation was conducted according to the protocol described by Hladík et al., 2023. Method accuracy (expressed as % BIAS) and precision (expressed as % RSD) were assessed through a spiking experiment. Pea seedlings (10 mg, homogenized) were extracted in 1 ml Na-phosphate buffer, and the extracts from five samples were pooled. The pooled extract was divided into 200 µl aliquots, with each aliquot spiked with 5 pmol of stable isotope-labelled standards. Unlabelled standards (1 or 10 pmol) were then added to the aliquots. The samples underwent purification using an in-tip µSPE method, and the concentrations of analytes were measured by HPLC-MS/MS with isotope dilution. Additionally, a separate set of plant extracts was processed without unlabelled standards, allowing for the subtraction of endogenous auxin metabolite levels to calculate recovery rates. Each sample was analysed in five replicates

Analyte	1 pmol			10 pmol		
	pmol	BIAS (%)	RSD (%)	pmol	BIAS (%)	RSD (%)
PAA	1.18 ± 0.17	-17	14	8.33 ± 0.16	17	2
PAA-Asp	1.02 ± 0.12	-2	12	9.52 ± 0.39	5	4
PAA-Glu	0.98 ± 0.07	2	7	9.45 ± 0.29	6	3
PAA-Val	0.71 ± 0.03	29	4	7.55 ± 0.53	25	7
PAA-Leu	1.05 ± 0.04	-5	4	10.65 ± 0.62	-6	6
PAA-Phe	1.00 ± 0.07	0	7	10.58 ± 0.49	-6	5
PAA-Trp	0.88 ± 0.06	12	6	10.29 ± 0.80	-3	8
PAA-glc*	8.16 ± 0.40	18	5	36.65 ± 2.32	27	6

* PAA-glc was spiked with 10 and 50 pmol

Table S4: Data collection and refinement statistics.

Enzyme	AtGH3.6	
	9FXD	9FWD
PDB ID	Asp + AMP	AMP
Ligand	Asp + AMP	AMP
Space group	P6 ₄	P6 ₄
Asymmetric unit	2 monomers	2 monomers
Unit cell (Å)		
a	197.9	197.0
b	197.9	197.0
c	65.3	65.2
α (°)	90.0	90.0
β (°)	90.0	90.0
γ (°)	120.0	120.0
Diffraction limits by STARANISO (Å)	2.13/2.13/1.74	2.61/ 2.61/1.93
Resolution (Å) ^a	98.9–1.74 (1.97-1.74)	85.3–1.93 (1.97-1.74)
Observed reflections	1474201 (59485)	1224027 (50777)
Unique reflections	96838 (4844)	58596 (2932)
Completeness spherical (%)	64.2 (10.3)	53.5 (8.7)
Completeness ellipsoidal (%)	96.0 (70.3)	95.4 (76.6)
<i>I</i> / σ (<i>I</i>)	11.3 (1.9)	14.6 (2.0)
<i>R</i> _{sym}	0.161 (1.429)	0.174 (1.727)
<i>R</i> _{meas}	0.166 (1.490)	0.179 (1.776)
<i>R</i> _{pim}	0.043 (0.421)	0.039 (0.411)
CC _{1/2} ^b	99.9 (70.5)	99.8 (63.7)
Amino acid residues	1170	1170
Water molecules	676	569
<i>R</i> _{cryst} (%)	0.1976	0.2027
<i>R</i> _{free} (%) ^c	0.2215	0.2402
RMSD bond lengths (Å)	0.009	0.008
RMSD bond angles (°)	1.06	1.01
Mean B value (Å ²):		
overall	33.5	44.5
protein chains (A/B)	32.9/34.1	43.1/46.4
water molecules	34.3	40.2
AMP (A/B)	18.2/21.3	28.2/32.3
Asp (A/B)	33.9/35.0	-/-
Ramachandran statistics (%) ^d :		
favored	98.9	98.4
outliers	0.0	0.0
Molprobitry Clashscore ^d	1.99	1.45
Molprobitry Overall score ^d	1.01	0.88

^a Numbers in parentheses represent values in the highest resolution shell.

^b CC_{1/2} stands for a percentage of correlation between intensities from a random half-dataset.

^c The 5% test set.

^d Generated with MolProbitry (Chen et al 2010).

Table S5: Ligand Lead Finder rank (LF), docking score and ΔG (Gibbs free energy) score for selected amino acid substrates and products. Docking was performed in FLARE (<https://www.cresset-group.com>).

Ligand	AtGH 3.5		AtGH 3.6	
	LF Rank score	LF ΔG kcal·mol ⁻¹	LF Rank score	LF ΔG kcal·mol ⁻¹
Asp	-5.315	-7.560	-6.615	-7.101
Glu	-5.164	-7.285	-6.669	-7.611
IAA-Asp	-8.795	-7.361	-9.786	-8.563
IAA-Glu	-7.841	-6.992	-9.510	-7.842
PAA-Asp	-7.107	-6.800	-8.560	-7.530
PAA-Glu	-7.235	-6.392	-8.662	-7.521

Supplemental references

Chen, V.B., Arendall, W.B. 3rd, Headd, J.J., Keedy, D.A., Immormino, R.M., Kapral, G.J., Murray, L.W., Richardson, J.S., Richardson, D.C. (2010). MolProbity: all-atom structure validation for macromolecular crystallography. *Acta Crystallogr D Biol Crystallogr.* **66**: 12-21.

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